

Reactions of Alkyl Orthotitanate. Part V. Reactions of Phenol with Ethyl and Isopropyl Titanates

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The action of hydrogen chloride as well as of ethanol and isopropanol on phenyl orthotitanate has been studied. Six mixed alkyl orthotitanates, $(OC_2H_5)_x Ti(OR)_{4-x}$ ($R = Et$ or Pr^i) have been prepared by causing phenol to react with alkyl orthotitanates in predetermined stoichiometric ratios.

Monohydric aliphatic alcohols have been shown to react with titanium tetrachloride (Jennings *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 637) to yield dichloride dialkoxide derivative. The reverse reaction, viz., the action of hydrogen chloride on alkyl orthotitanate, also yields the same dichloride dialkoxide derivative (Mehrotra, this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 733). The two reactions can be represented as :

Compared to above, alkyl orthosilicates (which can be readily prepared by causing silicon tetrachloride to act upon excess of alcohol) do not appear to react appreciably with hydrogen chloride at all, although absorption of hydrogen chloride to the extent of a mole per molecule of alkyl orthosilicate does occur (Cerrard and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 1690). This absorption of hydrogen chloride molecule could be interpreted either due to formation of trialkoxysilicon monochloride, $(OR)_3SiCl \cdot ROH$, or due to formation of an addition compound between the reactants, $Si(OR)_4 \cdot HCl$. The inability of the reaction product to yield mixed alkyl orthosilicate on being caused to react with a higher aliphatic alcohol, has lent support to the latter alternative (Mehrotra, *loc. cit.*). In view of these findings the reaction between titanium tetraphenoxide and hydrogen chloride has been studied.

Similar to the reaction between alkyl orthosilicate and hydrogen chloride, a mole of hydrogen chloride appears to react with a mole of titanium tetraphenoxide. This reaction could be represented either by formation of an addition compound (i) or by substitution of one of the phenoxy groups by chlorine atom (ii) :

In an effort to distinguish between the above two possible courses of reaction, the product dissolved in benzene was heated with an excess of isopropanol and anhydrous ammonia, when the corresponding reactions for (i) and (ii) could be

After removing the precipitated ammonium chloride, an orange-yellow solid was obtained from the filtrate. On the basis of the observed chemical analysis, the above product could be assigned one of the following formulas :

* or excess (the reactions were carried out in benzene).

** Reactions carried out in benzene.

This orange-yellow compound on being heated under reduced pressure gave out phenol, indicating that formula (II) is more probable. The final product corresponded in analysis to $Ti(C_6H_5O)_3(OPr^i)$. Hence reaction (ii) appears to be more probable when hydrogen chloride acts upon titanium tetraphenoxide.

Before accepting the above evidence, it was considered essential to study the replaceability of the phenoxy group in titanium tetraphenoxide with alkoxy (isopropoxy or ethoxy) groups. To reproduce closely the conditions of the possible reaction (iii), ammonia was passed in a mixture of titanium tetraphenoxide, dissolved in benzene, and excess isopropanol. An exothermic reaction appeared to take place in this system also and the final product was similar to the product finally obtained above, $(C_6H_5O)_3Ti.OPr^i$.

In view of the above, the evidence presented earlier for the formation of $TiCl(OC_6H_5)_3.C_6H_5OH$ by the reaction between titanium tetraphenoxide and hydrogen chloride becomes again inconclusive. These studies evidently show that the reaction of titanium tetrachloride with phenol together with reverse reaction, viz., the reaction between titanium tetraphenoxide and hydrogen chloride, is quite different from the corresponding reactions in case of alcohols or alkyl orthotitanates.

In view of the interesting results obtained in the above experiments, the reaction of titanium tetraphenoxide with ethanol or isopropanol (molar ratio 1:4), in refluxing benzene, was attempted when the mixed ethyl (or isopropyl) triphenyl orthotitanate appeared to be formed, as shown below :

The reaction between alkyl orthotitanates (ethyl and isopropyl) and phenol was investigated more thoroughly by causing them to react in predetermined stoichiometric ratios. As in the case of titanium tetrachloride (Funk and Rogler, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1944, **252**, 326), the four alkyl groups of alkyl orthotitanate molecule are successively replaced by the aryl groups in refluxing benzene. The replacement of last alkoxy group appears, however, to be comparatively much slow. The slow replaceability is understandable in view of the back reaction between titanium tetraphenoxide and ethanol or isopropanol, presented above.

The mixed alkyl aryl orthotitanates (I to III) can be prepared in quantitative yields by the reactions (i) to (iii).

* The reaction proceeds on heating under reduced pressure.

‡ Reaction proceeds at room temperature also.

** Very slow reaction.

The above reactions were carried out in refluxing benzene and the liberated alcohol, ROH, was fractionated azeotropically. The products were freed of benzene under reduced pressure. The mixed alkyl aryl orthotitanates are orange-yellow to deep yellow liquids and suffer thermal decomposition when attempted to distil them under reduced pressure. A gradual increase in intensity of the orange-yellow colour occurs as the number of aryl groups increases in the orthotitanate molecule; finally the phenyl orthotitanate is obtained, which is a scarlet solid, m.p. 155°, b.p. 226°/0.2 mm.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl and isopropyl orthotitanates were purified by fractionation under reduced pressure (Varma and Mehrotra, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1959, 8, 235). Ethanol (B.C.P.W., India) was first refluxed with freshly ignited quick lime for 6 hours and then distilled. The distillate was redistilled over sodium. Finally, it was dehydrated azeotropically with benzene before use; b.p. 78.3°. Isopropanol was first stored over aluminium isopropoxide for a fortnight and then fractionated over zirconium isopropoxide; b.p. 82.0°. Phenol (E. Merck) was purified by distillation, b.p. 180°. Benzene (B. D. H. AnalR) was stored over sodium wire for 2 days and fractionated, b.p. 80°.

The compounds were moistened with a few drops of aqueous ammonia, evaporated to dryness in an electric air-oven at 90°, and ignited to TiO₂. Ethanol and isopropanol in binary azeotropes with benzene were estimated (Mehrotra, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 904) by determining the unchanged chromic acid after a weighed sample of the azeotrope had been kept for 2 hours with an excess of the reagent (N-K₂Cr₂O₇ in 12.5% H₂SO₄). Phenoxy group was estimated by the method described by Kolthoff and Stenger ("Volumetric Analysis", Vol 2, Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1947, p. 216). After removing residual bromine by calomel, the liberated HBr was titrated against standard NaOH using bromocresol green indicator.

An all-glass apparatus fitted with interchangeable standard ground-glass joint was employed for entire experimentation and the reactions were protected from moisture.

Titanium Tetraphenoxide (Phenyl Orthotitanate).—To a well-cooled solution of titanium tetrachloride (5.0 g., 26.32 mM) in benzene (20 g.) was admitted phenol (15.0 g., 0.16 M). An exothermic reaction set in with evolution of HCl. The deep red reaction mixture was heated at 130–40° under reflux for 3 days till HCl could not be detected. The product was freed of the solvent under reduced pressure and crystallised from CCl₄ as a deep red crystalline mass (10.8 g.). The product produced only a very faint turbidity with silver nitrate solution. [Found: Ti, 9.24; C₆H₅O, 89.59. Calc. for Ti(OC₆H₅)₄.C₆H₅OH: Ti, 9.31; C₆H₅O, 90.69%].

The compound (8.9 g.) was heated under reduced pressure to 250°/0.2 mm, when a colorless liquid appeared, which readily solidified to a colorless crystalline mass (0.9 g.) (identified as phenol). Afterwards a deep red liquid, turning to a scarlet solid (5.8 g.), was obtained; b.p. 226°/0.2 mm, m.p. 155° (sealed tube). [Found: Ti, 11.34; C₆H₅O, 87.89. Calc. for Ti(OC₆H₅)₄: Ti, 11.38; C₆H₅O, 88.62%].

Reaction between Titanium Tetraphenoxide and Hydrogen Chloride.—To a red solution of titanium tetraphenoxide (4.73 g.) in benzene (45.0 g.) was bubbled slowly a current of dry hydrogen chloride for 2 hours. A black-red solution was obtained in the end, which was allowed to stand for a day. The reaction mixture was concentrated to 8–10 c.c. and set aside for crystallisation. The mother liquor was decanted and the deep red crystals (3.9 g.) were dried at 50°/1.0 mm for 2½ hours. (Found: Ti, 10.66; Cl, 8.1. C₂₄H₂₁O₄.TiCl requires Ti, 10.48; Cl, 7.77%).

Reaction between $C_{24}H_{21}O_4 \cdot TiCl$ and Isopropanol in presence of Ammonia.—A yellowish red solution was obtained on addition of isopropanol (4.1 g.) to the red solution of the preceding compound (1.8 g.) in benzene (20.0 g.). Anhydrous ammonia was slowly bubbled into the reaction mixture. An exothermic reaction occurred with formation of a white precipitate. The passage of ammonia was stopped after the evolution of heat had ceased; the reaction mixture was cooled to the room temperature. The white precipitate was filtered and washed with dry benzene. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure and the product was dried at $45^\circ/1.0$ mm for 2 hours. An orange-yellow solid (1.0 g.) was obtained. (Found: Ti, 9.95. $C_{27}H_{26}O_5Ti$ requires Ti, 9.98%).

The above compound (0.50 g.) was heated under reduced pressure when at $90^\circ/1.0$ mm, a colorless liquid appeared, which solidified to a colorless solid. It was soluble in water and was identified as phenol. The residue left was deep orange in colour (0.45 g.). (Found: Ti, 11.98. $C_{21}H_{22}O_4Ti$ requires Ti, 12.40%).

Reaction between Titanium Tetrphenoxide and Ethanol (molar ratio 1:4).—Titanium tetraphenoxide (6.90 g., 16.44 mM), benzene (19.0 g.) and ethanol (3.04 g., 66.08 mM) were heated under reflux for 3 hours. The solvent was distilled under reduced pressure from the reaction mixture and the product was dried at $30^\circ/1$ mm. A bright orange solid (9.1 g. Ti, 8.92%) was obtained, which was refluxed gently with ether (100 c.c.) for 3 hours. The supernatant liquor along with some solid was decanted and the remaining solid was dried at $60^\circ/3.5$ mm. An orange-yellow solid (8.4 g.) was obtained. (Found: Ti, 10.15. $C_{26}H_{28}O_5Ti$ requires Ti, 10.28%).

Reaction between Titanium Tetrphenoxide and Isopropanol (molar ratio 1:4).—To a deep red solution of titanium tetraphenoxide (11.36 g., 27.04 mM) in benzene (25.0 g.) was added isopropanol (6.68 g., 0.11 M). An orange-yellow solution was obtained, which was heated under reflux for 3 hours. The reaction mixture was freed of the solvent under reduced pressure and the product was dried at $30^\circ/1.0$ mm. A bright yellow solid (14.5 g. Ti, 9.26%) was obtained. It was gently refluxed with ether (100 c.c.) for 3 hours. The supernatant liquor was decanted. A bright yellow powder (10.2 g.) was obtained after drying the product at $30^\circ/1$ mm for 2 hours. (Found: Ti, 10.03. $C_{27}H_{28}O_5Ti$ requires Ti, 9.98%).

Reaction between Titanium Tetrphenoxide and Isopropanol in presence of Ammonia.—To a yellow solution consisting of titanium tetraphenoxide (1.1 g.), benzene (10.0 g.), and isopropanol (14.0 g.) was passed anhydrous ammonia slowly, when heat was evolved with a slight white turbidity. The reaction mixture at the end of the reaction was filtered and left to settle overnight. The clear filtrate was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure; the product was dried at $80-90^\circ/1$ mm, when a colorless liquid turning to a transparent solid (identified as phenol) appeared. The drying was continued till the appearance of the colorless liquid stopped. Finally an orange solid (0.92 g.) was obtained. (Found: Ti, 11.98. $C_{21}H_{22}O_4Ti$ requires Ti, 12.40%).

Reaction between Ethyl Orthotitanate and Phenol (molar ratio 1:1).—An exothermic reaction occurred on addition of phenol (3.42 g., 36.34 mM) to ethyl orthotitanate (8.10 g., 35.53 mM). The orange-yellow reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight. The product was freed of volatile fractions by drying it at $40^\circ/1.0$ mm. An orange-yellow, thick liquid (10.0 g.) dissolving in benzene was obtained. [Found: Ti, 17.16; C_6H_5O , 32.53. $C_6H_5O \cdot Ti(OEt)_3$ requires Ti, 17.36; C_6H_5O , 33.73%].

In an attempt to distil the compound (6.35 g.), it was heated to $210^\circ/1.0$ mm, when a colorless liquid (4.03 g.) with a yellowish colour collected in the receiver; b.p. $134^\circ/0.9$ mm. (Found: Ti, 19.93%).

The above distillate (3.09 g.) was fractionated under reduced pressure. The middle fraction, a colorless liquid (2.21 g.), was collected at 120.5°/0.9 mm. [Found: Ti, 20.79; OEt, 80.28. Calc. for $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_4$: Ti, 20.99; OEt, 79.01%].

Reaction between Isopropyl Orthotitanate and Phenol (molar ratio 1:1).—Isopropyl orthotitanate (4.27 g., 15.04 mM), phenol (1.40 g., 14.89 mM), and benzene (60 g.) were stirred together to yield a deep yellow solution. It was refluxed under the fractionating column for an hour. The azeotrope (b.p. 71°) was slowly fractionated out dropwise. After collection of nearly 4 c.c., the distillate attained a b.p. of 73°; at this stage the withdrawal of the azeotrope was suspended and the reaction mixture was allowed to reflux for another hour. The azeotrope was again withdrawn dropwise till the distillate acquired a constant temperature of 80°. The rest of the distillate was collected separately under a high reflux ratio, 1:20. The reaction mixture was evaporated to a deep yellow, fairly mobile liquid (4.80 g.) at 50°/1.0 mm. The compound is readily miscible with benzene. [Found: isopropanol, 0.89 g. in azeotrope, against 0.90 g. calc. for 1 mole (for orthotitanate taken). [Found: Ti, 15.13; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 29.46. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}\cdot\text{Ti}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ requires Ti, 15.06; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 29.27%].

Reaction between Ethyl Orthotitanate and Phenol (molar ratio 1:2).—(a). To a solution of ethyl orthotitanate (3.82 g., 16.75 mM) in benzene (41.0 g.) was introduced phenol (3.15 g., 33.51 mM). On stirring, a noticeable heat was produced. The orange-coloured solution was refluxed at 110–20° for 3 hours, after which the azeotrope (b.p. 68°) was carefully fractionated till the distillate attained a constant temperature of 80°. The subsequent fractions were collected separately under a high reflux ratio of 1:20. On drying the reaction product at 50°/1.0 mm., an orange-red thick liquid (5.57 g.), miscible with benzene, was obtained. [Found: ethanol in azeotrope, 1.47 g. against 1.51 g. calc. for 2 moles (for orthotitanate taken)]. [Found: Ti, 14.77; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 56.0. $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O})_2\cdot\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_2$ requires Ti, 14.79; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 57.41%].

(b). Phenol (5.70 g., 60.64 mM) was allowed to react with ethyl orthotitanate (6.88 g., 30.18 mM) in refluxing benzene (20.0 g.) for 4 hours. An orange-red thick liquid (10.0 g.) was obtained. [Found: Ti, 14.53; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 55.91. $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O})_2\cdot\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_2$ requires Ti, 14.79; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 57.41%].

The above compound (7.02 g.) was heated to 240°/1.0 mm. A few drops of a light yellow liquid first appeared, followed by an orange-red liquid (4.58 g.) at 210–15°/1.0 mm. [Found: Ti, 16.19; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 41.07%].

The distillate (3.5 g.) from above was fractionated under reduced pressure. A faint yellow mobile liquid (0.92 g.) collected at 120°/0.9 mm. [Found: Ti, 21.00; OEt, 80.54. Calc. for $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_4$: Ti, 20.99; OEt, 79.01%].

Next, an orange-yellow liquid (0.86 g.) was collected at 211°/0.5 mm. (Found: Ti, 16.9%).

Finally a deep red liquid, immediately solidifying to a deep red solid (0.4 g.), was collected at 235°/0.5 mm. (Found: Ti, 11.66%).

Reaction between Isopropyl Orthotitanate and Phenol (molar ratio 1:2).—Phenol (3.39 g., 36.06 mM) was treated with isopropyl orthotitanate (5.24 g., 18.45 mM) in refluxing benzene (50.0 g.). The liberated isopropanol was carefully fractionated completely. A dark red viscous liquid (6.78 g.), miscible in benzene, was obtained after drying the product at 50°/1.0 mm. [Found: isopropanol in azeotrope, 2.19 g. against 2.21 g. calc. for 2 moles (for orthotitanate taken)]. [Found: Ti, 13.58; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 52.12. $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O})_2\cdot\text{Ti}(\text{OPr}^i)_2$ requires Ti, 13.61; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 52.84%].

The compound (4.76 g.) was heated under reduced pressure at 190° when a faintly yellow, mobile liquid (2.99 g.) having a boiling range 67-68.5°/1.5 mm was collected. [Found: Ti, 17.04; OPr^i , 85.61. Calc. for $\text{Ti}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$: Ti, 16.85; OPr^i , 83.15%].

Reaction between Ethyl Orthotitanate and Phenol (molar ratio 1:3).—Ethyl orthotitanate (4.29 g., 18.82 mM), phenol (5.38 g., 57.23 mM), and benzene (40.0 g.) were heated at 110-20° under a fractionating column. The ethanol produced in the reaction was completely removed azeotropically. The product was dried at 40°/1.0 mm. A very thick, viscous, orange-red liquid (7.34 g.), which set to a transparent glass like mass, was obtained. Deep red crystals separated from its benzene solution after a fortnight. [Found: ethanol, 2.41 g. against 2.54 g. calc. for 3 moles (for orthotitanates taken)]. [Found: Ti, 12.40; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 72.02. $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O})_3\text{TiOEt}$ requires Ti, 12.87; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 75.06%].

The above compound (3.65 g.) was heated to 240°/0.8 mm. An orange liquid (0.8 g.) collected at 217-24°/2.0 mm. (Found: Ti, 15.74; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 60.59%).

Reaction between Isopropyl Orthotitanate and Phenol (molar ratio 1:3).—An orange-yellow solution was obtained by stirring together isopropyl orthotitanate (3.55 g., 12.49 mM), phenol (3.54 g., 37.66 mM), and benzene (43.0 g.) The solution was refluxed under the column at 110-20° for an hour, after which the isopropanol liberated in the reaction was completely fractionated. On drying the product at 80°/1.5 mm, a deep red, thick, viscous liquid (5.08 g.), soluble in benzene was obtained. [Found: isopropanol in azeotrope, 2.19 g. against 2.25 g. calc. for 3 moles (for orthotitanate taken)]. [Found: Ti, 12.43; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 71.53. $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O})_3\text{Ti.OPr}^i$ requires Ti, 12.40; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 72.30%].

Reaction between Ethyl Orthotitanate and Phenol (molar ratio 1:4).—Phenol (7.50 g., 79.7 mM) was treated with ethyl orthotitanate (4.41 g., 19.35 mM) in refluxing benzene (71.0 g.). The ethanol produced in the reaction was carefully fractionated over a period of 11 hours. The reaction mixture was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure and the product was dried at 80°/1.0 mm. A red powder (8.4 g.) was obtained, soluble in benzene, m.p. 154-55° (in a sealed tube). (Found: ethanol in azeotrope, 3.44 g. against 3.48 g. contained in orthotitanate taken). [Found: Ti, 11.30; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 87.90. Calc. for $\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_4$: Ti, 11.38; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 88.62%].

The above compound (3.7 g.) gave a deep red liquid, b.p. 226°/0.2 mm, which readily solidified to a scarlet solid (2.2 g.) [Found: Ti, 11.32; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 87.90. Calc. for $\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_4$: Ti, 11.38; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$, 88.62%].

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